

similar morphological characters

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	Coproporus CVB11	Coproporus CVB71	Coproporus CVB12	Coproporus CVB81
Female sternite VIII		no female		
Female tergite VIII		no female		
Male sternite VIII				
Male tergite VIII				
Aedeagus				